

IMMUNOLOGICAL FEATURES IN PATIENTS WITH ARTERIAL HYPERTENSION AGAINST THE BACKGROUND OF ALLERGIC DISEASES

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The aim of the article is to study the level of cytokines in patients with arterial hypertension associated with allergies.

Materials and methods. Clinical and immunological examination was conducted on 65 patients with arterial hypertension, who were in the multidisciplinary clinic of the Center for Development of Professional Qualifications of Medical Workers, Tashkent. The age of patients ranged from 45 to 65 years. Patients were divided into 2 groups: 42 patients with hypertension - group 1 and 23 patients with hypertension + allergic diseases. All patients underwent clinical, instrumental, and laboratory examinations. Immunological studies were conducted using the ELISA method to study the level of pro- and anti-inflammatory cytokines in the serum of peripheral blood using test systems of JSC Vector Best (RF).

Results. In hypertension, elevated levels of IL-1 are observed, IL-6, and TNF α . At the same time, the level of anti-inflammatory cytokine IL-4 remains within the control values. In the combined course of hypertension and AD, cytokine imbalance is characterized by an even more significant increase in the serum concentration of pro-inflammatory cytokines IL-1 β , IL-6, and TNF- α and a reliable rise in the serum concentration of IL-4.

Conclusion. The study of the cytokine profile and inflammation biomarkers in hypertension in combination with AD will allow for early diagnosis of vascular disorders and optimization of preventive measures in patients with arterial hypertension with a comorbid course.

Keywords: *arterial hypertension, allergy, inflammation, immune system, cytokines.*

In recent years, the role of inflammation in the development of cardiovascular diseases has attracted great interest. Vascular wall tension and endothelial dysfunction initiate the production of a wide range of cytokines, migration, and accumulation of inflammatory cells, which is one of the links in the pathogenesis of arterial hypertension (AH) and atherosclerosis [1-5,8,11]. Inflammation initiates the proliferation of smooth muscle cells of the media and is a trigger factor for vascular wall remodeling, which in turn leads to an increase in blood pressure [7,9,11].

Cytokines are key mediators of intercellular interactions, including in the process of inflammation [6]. Inflammation is the main pathophysiological substrate of cardiovascular diseases [9]. Increased expression of inflammatory mediators by the endothelium underlies atherosclerotic damage to the vascular wall [Kofler S. et al., 2005]. Thus, a "vicious circle" arises, and the process of progression of damage to target organs of hypertension accelerates.

Allergy has become one of the most common pathologies worldwide. According to literature data, the prevalence of allergic diseases in various regions of Uzbekistan ranges from 15 to 35%. Some of the most common allergic diseases are allergic rhinitis, atopic dermatitis, and atopic bronchial asthma. AD is a global health problem, that occurs in almost all countries of the world and affects from 15 to 40% of people of all ages [6]. Allergic diseases are characterized by the presence of immunologically conditioned IgE-dependent inflammation

caused by a causative allergen. In particular, impaired nasal breathing during an exacerbation of allergic rhinitis leads to snoring, and the development of hypopnea and apnea during sleep [11,12,13 14]. Sleep apnea is a known risk factor for hypertension (HTN) and CVD, inducing hypoxemia, hypercapnia, decreased serum pH, and increased catecholamine concentrations [14].

Thus, the study of the pathogenesis of hypertension associated with AD and its comorbid course, the development and implementation in practical healthcare of measures to predict, identify, and prevent immune and vascular disorders in patients with hypertension are currently urgent tasks in modern medicine [6,10,14].

Purpose of the study – to study the level of cytokines in patients with arterial hypertension associated with allergies.

Materials and methods. Clinical and immunological examination was conducted on 65 patients with arterial hypertension, who were in the multidisciplinary clinic of the Center for Development of Professional Qualifications of Medical Workers, Tashkent. The age of the patients ranged from 45 to 65 years. The patients were divided into 2 groups: 42 patients with hypertension - group 1 and the 2nd - 23 patients in whom hypertension was combined with allergic diseases (AD). All patients underwent a comprehensive examination based on clinical, instrumental, and laboratory studies. Of the examined, 38 were men (58.5%), and 27 women (41.5%). Inclusion criteria: patients with symptoms of AD and hypertension of stage I-II according to instrumental research methods, grades 1-2 according to the level of systolic and diastolic blood pressure. The diagnosis of hypertension was made according to the recommendations of the All-Russian Scientific Society of Cardiologists and the ESH/ESC 2018 recommendations [7]. The study did not include patients with secondary hypertension, malignant hypertension, acute inflammatory processes, and chronic ones in the exacerbation stage, hematological diseases, oncological diseases, alcoholism, drug addiction, connective tissue diseases, diseases of the central and peripheral nervous system, mental illness, chronic heart failure of III-IV functional classes according to the New York Heart Association and the presence of hemodynamically significant heart defects.

All patients had permanent jobs and reported experiencing stressful situations in their daily lives.

Immunological studies were carried out by studying the level of pro- (IL-1 β , IL-6, and TNF) and anti-inflammatory (IL-4) cytokines in the serum of peripheral blood by the ELISA method using the test systems of JSC Vector Best (RF). The control group consisted of 30 practically healthy individuals, with normal blood pressure, not suffering from cardiovascular pathology and AD, comparable in gender and age with groups 1 and 2 (mean age 45.41 $\pm$ 2.04 years).

Statistical data processing was carried out on a PC using Microsoft Office Excel 2007 and the statistical package Statistica 7.0 (StatSoft Inc, USA).

Research results and their discussion. The conducted study of the anamnestic data of the examined patients showed that the age varied from 45 to 65 and above. A more detailed analysis showed the following (Table 1). As can be seen from the data presented in Table No. 1, 4.76% of patients with hypertension were under 45 years of age (2). The maximum number of patients were aged 55 to 60 years - 30.23% (13), and 28.57% (7) were from 50 to 55 years. Patients aged 60 and above were 16.66% (7).

Table 1

Distribution of patients by age history, abs/%

Groups	Up to 45 years	45-50 years old	50-55 years old	55-60 years old	60 years and above
1st group n=42	2/4.76	8/19,04	12/28.57	13/30.23	7/16.66
2nd group n=23	5 /21.74	7/30.43	5/21.74	4/30.43	2/8.69
Counter gr. n=30	4/13.33	7/23.33	8/26.66	5/16.66	6/20,0

The age history of patients with combined hypertension and allergic diseases showed that the maximum number of patients were between 40 and 50 years old. According to the anamnesis, the blood pressure (BP) in patients ranged from 150/80 mm Hg to 165/85 mm Hg. Anamnestic analysis of somatic diseases showed that patients with hypertension had metabolic syndrome, type 2 diabetes, bronchial asthma, gastrointestinal diseases, etc. (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Concomitant somatic diseases in examined patients, %

As can be seen from the data presented in Fig. 1, in the 1st group of patients with arterial hypertension, metabolic syndrome was most frequently encountered in patients – 29/69.04%, and in the 2nd group, metabolic syndrome was encountered in 1/3 of patients - 7/30.43%. Diabetes mellitus (DM) was suffered by 20 patients (47.61%) in the 1st group, and by 8 patients (34.78%) in the 2nd group. Diseases of the thyroid gland, gastrointestinal tract, and urinary system (US) were encountered approximately equally. Diseases of the upper and lower

respiratory tract (ULRT) were more common in patients with arterial hypertension in association with allergic diseases – 20/86.95%.

Analysis of allergic diseases in the group of patients with combined pathology showed that these were mainly allergic rhinitis - 18/78.26%. Atopic dermatitis was observed in 3 patients (13.04%) and 2 patients had atopic bronchial asthma (8.7%).

When analyzing anamnestic data, it was revealed that 1/3 of patients in the 2nd group had a hereditary predisposition to allergic diseases.

Studies on the cytokine status showed that the level of proinflammatory cytokines was elevated in all patients with hypertension (Table 2).

Table 2.

Level of pro- and anti-inflammatory cytokines in examined patients, M±m

Cytokines, pg/ml	Control group, n=30	1-group, n=43	2nd group, n=23
IL-1β	26.3 ± 1.8	56.7 ± 2.1*	73.4 ± 2.4 * **
IL-4	6.7 ± 0.6	7.4 ± 0.65	13.8 ± 1.3* **
IL-6	17.9 ± 1.5	64.8 ± 2.4*	76.5 ± 2.7 * **
TNFα	21.4 ± 1.6	58.9 ± 2.3*	69.7 ± 2.6* **

Note: * Values are reliable relative to the control group

** Values are reliable relative to the 1st group

(P<0.05 -0.001)

As can be seen from the data presented in Table 1, the level of IL-1β in patients with AG is increased by 2 times compared to the data of the control group (P<0.01). In patients with combined pathology, the level of the proinflammatory cytokine IL-1β is 2.8 times higher than the values of the control group (P<0.001) and significantly higher than the values of the 1st group (P<0.05). Analysis of the results showed that in 63% of patients. In patients with hypertension, elevated concentrations of IL-6 are found in the blood, with the elevated level being 3.6 times higher (P<0.001). In patients with hypertension against the background of AD, this indicator is even higher compared to the control group data (P<0.001). In terms of the diversity of cellular sources of production and targets of biological action, IL-6 is one of the most active cytokines, which takes part in the implementation of the immune response and inflammatory reactions, showing its activity not only in adipose tissue but also systemically [A.S. Simbirtsev, 2016].

The course of hypertension affects the synthesis of another proinflammatory cytokine, TNFα, which is increased by 2.7 times relative to the control group (P<0.001). Against the background of allergic diseases, the level of TNFα is increased even more. Consequently, nonspecific inflammation is observed in arterial hypertension, which can lead to the development of cardiovascular complications (myocardial infarction, stroke, heart and kidney failure) [7, 8].

The level of anti-inflammatory cytokine - IL-4 in patients with AG was at the level of control values. However, in patients of the 2nd group, the level of IL-4 was increased by 2 times (P<0.01). Therefore, in the combined pathology of AG with AD, activation of not only pro-inflammatory but also anti-inflammatory cytokines occurs.

Discussion of results thus, in the comorbid course of hypertension in combination with allergic diseases, the development of nonspecific inflammation is observed, which aggravates the course of both hypertension and allergic diseases.

Several mechanisms explain the possible relationship between the development of AD and damage to target organs. Excessive activation of angiotensin II causes several adverse effects in the form of vasoconstriction, activation of aldosterone synthesis, myocardial hypertrophy, proliferation of smooth muscle cells, activation of lipid peroxidation processes, etc. Angiotensin II causes the expression of proinflammatory molecules in the vascular wall, which leads to the accumulation of monocytes at the site of its damage. In endothelial cells, angiotensin II regulates the expression of intracellular adhesion molecules (IAM) and E-selectin, which contributes to the development of endothelial dysfunction. In smooth muscle cells, angiotensin II stimulates the synthesis of IL-1 β and IL-6, causing nonspecific inflammation in the vascular wall. There is evidence that IL-6 as a factor of non-specific inflammation (NI) plays an important role in damage to target organs in the early stages of hypertension due to the unity of neurohumoral mechanisms of the development of non-specific inflammation and damage to target organs [13]. Under conditions of inflammation, endothelial activation of inflammatory mediators such as IL-6, IL-1 β , and TNF α , which, in turn, increase endothelial dysfunction, closing the vicious circle [9]. These changes are enhanced by a comorbid condition, and the synthesis of anti-inflammatory cytokines is activated. The results suggest that an increase in the level of TNF is probably associated with the onset of arrhythmia in patients with hypertension, which is confirmed by data from other studies. Naoyuki Sata et al. noted a significant increase in the level of TNF- α during paroxysms of atrial fibrillation (AF). A similar trend was found by scientists in interleukin-6 [14].

It is known that proinflammatory cytokines (TNF, IL-1, IL-6) have the properties to induce the development of endothelial dysfunction, for example, TNF activates the migration of leukocytes and causes the expression of adhesion molecules on the surface of endothelial cells. The consequence of this is the adhesion of neutrophils, monocytes, and lymphocytes with the development of inflammatory infiltration of the vascular wall [5].

Thus, an increase in the concentration of pro- and anti-inflammatory cytokines in the comorbid course of hypertension indicates the importance of this link in homeostasis in the pathogenesis of the disease.

Conclusions

In patients with arterial hypertension, the level of proinflammatory cytokines (IL-1 β , IL-6, and TNF α) is significantly higher than the control values.

In patients with hypertension against the background of allergic diseases, not only the level of proinflammatory cytokines but also anti-inflammatory (IL-4) cytokines is significantly increased.

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